

Studies on some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part IV*. Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies on Beryllium Ferrocyanide

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The reaction between potassium ferrocyanide and beryllium chloride has been studied spectrophotometrically. From the results it is concluded that (i) decomposition of K_4FeCy_6 is a slow reaction, (ii) the reaction is dependent on the concentration of beryllium ions, and (iii) it can best be studied at $450m\mu$.

Appearance of the blue colour in slightly acidic solution of potassium ferrocyanide in presence of beryllium ions has been explained on the basis of decomposition of potassium ferrocyanide and the subsequent formation of Prussian blue. Conductometric titrations carried out at 30° , 60° , and 80° give evidence of the formation of an adsorption complex, $K_2BeFeCy_6.K_4FeCy_6$.

An interesting reaction, worth considering amongst the less familiar metal ferrocyanogen complexes, is the formation of beryllium ferrocyanide by the interaction of beryllium with potassium ferrocyanide. References on this compound are rarely met with in the literature. Recently the author came across a reference on the estimation of beryllium by ferrocyanide (Miss Zutshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1960, Part III, p. 191) where the reaction was assumed to be simple enough for indirect estimation of beryllium by titrating the excess of potassium ferrocyanide after precipitating beryllium as beryllium ferrocyanide. Our experience shows that the reaction is not so simple as that to be satisfactorily used for the estimation of beryllium in solutions. On the other hand, the reaction is enshrouded with a number of complexities, which should be taken into account while studying it.

Preliminary experiments reveal the following facts: (i) When dilute solutions of beryllium chloride and potassium ferrocyanide are mixed, a blue colour develops in a few moments; a turbidity appears on keeping it for four to five hours. (ii) On increasing the pH of the beryllium solution (just before precipitation of the oxide sets in; $pH=4.5$) a blue colour develops although it takes a little more time to do so. (iii) Dilute solutions, when mixed at a temperature near about 70° , give a white precipitate almost instantaneously although invariably tarnished with a green colour (turning to blue on keeping for more than 20 minutes at this temperature). (iv) On adding a concentrated solution of beryllium chloride ($M/2; M/5$) to potassium ferrocyanide solution, precipitation slowly sets in even at the room temperature.

Considering the above interesting facts for the reaction, it was thought worthwhile to carry out its detailed study. In this communication two aspects of the problem have been dealt with: (i) spectrophotometric study of the blue product formed on mixing the reactants and (ii) conductometric studies for the elucidation of the composition of the beryllium ferrocyanide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The beryllium chloride solution was obtained by adding a calculated amount of HCl to a weighed amount of beryllium oxide. After heating the resulting solution was filtered. A small portion of it was then estimated gravimetrically as BeO. Fresh solutions were prepared occasionally to avoid hydrolysis.

A concentrated solution of K_4FeCy_6 was prepared by dissolving recrystallised sample in doubly distilled water and the strength determined by titrating with potassium permanganate of known strength. The solution was stored in a dark-coloured bottle.

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Spectrophotometric Determinations

Beckman DU spectrophotometer was used for the measurements. The cell was 1 cm corex type and the light source was a tungsten lamp.

Absorption experiments were performed after mixing 0.2c.c., 0.4c.c.....1.8c.c., 2.0c.c. 10^{-2} M-BeCl₂ with 10.0c.c. of 10^{-1} M-K₄FeCy₆, making the total volume to 12.0c.c. in each case. For one particular mixture, the absorption was noted for a number of wave lengths (between 350m μ and 500 m μ). It was observed that with increasing wave length the absorption value went on decreasing. At 350 m μ it was highest, so much that with mixtures containing large proportions of beryllium, the O.D. was near about 2. The wave lengths found suitable to work with were in the region 400 to 555 m μ . The absorption values at 460 and 500 m μ for the mixtures, kept overnight, are as shown in Table I

TABLE I

10 ⁻² M-BeCl ₂ added to 10c.c. of 10 ⁻¹ M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ (c.c.)		..	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.0
O.D. at 460 m μ	..	..	0.78	0.80	0.90	0.92	0.90	1.02	1.12	1.23	1.38	1.70
O.D. at 500 m μ	..	..	0.315	0.408	0.37	0.47	0.42	0.46	0.53	0.53	0.67	0.78

Table I evidently shows that the O.D. values increase with the increase in the concentrations of beryllium ions although irregularities are observed in certain cases. This may be due to the turbidity appearing in the mixtures on keeping overnight.

In view of the fact that it took some time for the blue colour to develop, the variation in the O.D. for three different solutions: (I) 0.5c.c., (II) 0.7c.c., (III) 0.9c.c. of 10^{-2} M-BeCl₂ in 10c.c. of 10^{-1} M-K₄FeCy₆ (total volume made to 12c.c.) at different time intervals were measured.

TABLE II

Time.	Wave length.	Optical density of solutions.		
		(I).	(II).	(III).
3.45 p.m.	450 m μ	1.105	0.160	0.170
4.20	450	0.200	0.280	0.330
4.55	450	0.282	0.380	0.420
5.25	450	0.298	0.488	0.520
6.00	450	0.395	0.560	0.665
6.35	450	0.458	0.690	0.830

N.B. The solutions were mixed at 3.30 p.m.

Since the addition of a fairly concentrated solution of HCl to potassium ferrocyanide solution effected decomposition of the latter, resulting in the development of a blue colour, it was deemed necessary to carry out absorption experiments in presence of HCl. The three mixtures mixed were: (I) 0.5c.c., (II) 0.7c.c., and (III) 0.9c.c. of 10^{-1} M-HCl in 10.0c.c. of 10^{-1} M-K₃FeCy₆. The total volume was made to 12.0c.c. in each case.

TABLE III

Time.	Wave length.	Optical density of solutions.		
		(I).	(II).	(III).
11.40 a.m.	450 m μ	0.125	0.24	0.345
12.0	450	0.190	0.32	0.40
12.30 p.m.	450	0.215	0.36	0.47
12.50	450	0.240	0.40	0.52
1.10	450	0.285	0.465	0.60

N. B. The solutions were mixed at 11 a.m.

In the preliminary experiments it was found that in a large number of cases the O.D. increased with increase in the concentration of Be^{2+} ions for mixtures kept overnight. To have a more precise idea of the influence of the concentration of the beryllium ions, measurements were made at different time intervals (40 minutes, $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and 2 hours) for five concentrations of beryllium ions in the mixture (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9 c.c. of $10^{-2} M$ - BeCl_2 , added to 10 c.c. $10^{-1} M$ - K_4FeCy_6 ; total volume made to 12.0 c.c.).

TABLE IV

Time interval.	Wave length.	Optical density of solutions.				
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
50 mins	450m μ	0.037	0.150	0.200	0.280	0.315
$1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.	450	0.050	0.194	0.270	0.365	0.420
2	450	0.055	0.260	0.298	0.480	0.520

Conductometric Titrations

The conductivity measurements were carried out by a W.T.W. conductivity bridge with a dip type conductivity cell. The beryllium chloride solution was neutralised with a few drops of strong caustic soda solution to increase the pH of the solution (pH 4.5). With concentrated solutions of the reactants, a white precipitate was obtained even at the room temperature, the supernatant liquid having a light greenish colour. This colour became darker with time and increasing temperature; volume correction (Davies, "The Conductivity of the Solutions"; Taylor, "A Treatise of Physical Chemistry, Chapter XIII) was made by multiplying the observed conductance by the factor $(V+v)/V$, where V refers to the volume of the reactant originally taken in the cell and v is the volume added. The titrations were carried out with different concentrations of the reactants at 30°, 60°, and 80°. Titrations with K_4FeCy_6 in the cell were not successful. Some of the results are summarised below.

TABLE V

BeCl_2 soln.	K_4FeCy_6 from the curve.		Ratio at the inflection point.
	Temp.=30°±0.1°.		$\text{Be}^{2+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$.
10c.c. of $M/2$	12c.c. of $M/5$		2.081:1
10 $M/5$	9.6 $M/5$		10:9.66
9 $M/5$ +1c.c. EtOH	9.0 $M/5$		1:1
Temp.=60±0.1°.			
20 $M/1000$	2c.c. & 3.9c.c. of $M/100$		1:1 & 1:1.95
20 $M/500$	4 & 8.5 $M/100$		1:1 & 1:2.1
20 $M/100$	2 & 4.25 $M/100$		1:1 & 1:2.12
Temp.=80±0.1°.			
20 $M/1000$	1.9 & 3.9 $M/100$		1.05:1 & 1:1.95
20 $M/500$	4.0 & 8.5 $M/100$		1:1 & 1:2.1

DISCUSSION

The variations in the optical densities of the various mixtures with time bring out two important facts regarding the nature of beryllium ferrocyanide reaction: (i) Decomposition of potassium ferrocyanide is a slow reaction and takes place with a definite velocity, (ii) the reaction is dependent on the concentration of beryllium ions, being faster at higher concentrations of beryllium. On plotting the O.D. against time (Table II), it was found that a break in the time—absorption curve occurred after a fixed period (90 minutes) for the different concentrations of Be^{2+} . The behaviour is rather significant and can be

explained by assuming that altogether different reactions take place in the early stages and thereafter. Further support to this viewpoint was forthcoming when curves were drawn between concentrations of beryllium ions and O.D. after 50 minutes, 90 minutes, and 120 minutes respectively (Table IV). There it is found that the curves for 120 minutes show an irregular behaviour and are quite different from those for the time periods 50 minutes and 90 minutes. From this it may be concluded that some sort of interaction of beryllium chloride and potassium ferrocyanide is also taking place simultaneously with the decomposition of the latter.

A comparison of the O.D. values in presence of Be^{2+} (Table II) and those in presence of varying amounts of $10^{-1} M$ -HCl (Table III) reveals that although the absorption values with hydrochloric acid are higher than those for Be^{2+} in the beginning, the development of blue colour is more rapid in presence of beryllium chloride than with solutions containing HCl (e.g. in approximately two hours the O.D. in presence of Be^{2+} increases from 0.17 to 0.58, whereas in presence of HCl it changes from 0.345 to 0.6). Moreover, on keeping the mixture for longer periods, solutions containing Be^{2+} gave very high values for O.D. when compared to solutions containing HCl (where some slight turbidity also appeared). These observations, combined with the fact that beryllium solution is only slightly acidic, indicate that the rapid and intense development of blue colour is not merely due to the hydrogen ions and that Be^{2+} ions are also involved in the reaction. The role of Be^{2+} in this reaction is not easy to see and appears to be a moot question. The hydrogen ions derived from the hydrolysis of the beryllium salts, combined with the slow aggregation of colloidal beryllium ferrocyanide (with a little beryllium hydroxide), may be responsible for the development of the blue colour from the slow decomposition of hydroferrocyanic acid in solution. The Prussian blue thus formed is likely to be adsorbed on the various sol particles of growing size, which increase the optical density of the solution over that of the solutions containing only HCl.

The spectrophotometric studies also show that the reaction can best be studied at $450 \text{ m}\mu$ and that the possibility of the reaction to be used as a micro test for detection of Be^{2+} cannot be completely ruled out.

Composition of Beryllium Ferrocyanide

Direct conductometric titrations with concentrated solutions of the reactants give a ratio $2\text{Be}^{2+}:1 \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$ as well as a ratio of 1:1. This would mean the existence of two complexes having the formulas Be_2FeCy_6 and $\text{K}_2\text{BeFeCy}_6$. Since the appearance of the white precipitate at the room temperature on mixing beryllium chloride and potassium ferrocyanide takes some time, it is quite probable that the compound Be_2FeCy_6 is formed with $M/2$ solution, whereas the complex $\text{K}_2\text{BeFeCy}_6$ is formed with dilute solutions ($M/5$).

Titration carried out at temperatures 60° and 80° give two breaks. From these it may be concluded that besides the formation of the complex $\text{K}_2\text{BeFeCy}_6$, an addition complex, $\text{K}_2\text{BeFeCy}_6 \cdot \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$, one mole of potassium ferrocyanide adsorbed per mole of the complex, is also formed.

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